

APPROACH OF MAQĀSĪD ASH-SHARĪ'AH IN CONTROLLING KIDNAPPING IN NORTHERN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Crime is almost part and parcel of all societies, especially in our contemporary times. Kidnapping has become a worrisome menace in Northern Nigeria. The aim of this research is to explore the objectives of Islamic law (Maqāsīd Ash-Sharī'ah) on crime control and management so as to have a decent environment with minimal commitment to avoidable crimes. The method adopted is through the perusal of related literatures available in the library and online as secondary sources, while Qur'ān and Prophetic traditions provide the primary sources. Interviews was also conducted. The findings indicates that the high rate of unemployment among the youth after graduation from colleges, polytechnics and universities is a major cause of this evil act of kidnapping. Factors responsible for the crime are absence of God's consciousness by those that involved in the act, self-enrichment with quick money, inadequate security personnel and injustice from the side of Northern Nigerian governors are also contributing in this regards. The engagement of youth in different skills acquisition, provision of employment by private and public sectors can help in reducing the ungodly act, the paper recommends among others, that justice must be ensured at all levels from federal, state and local governments which can contribute immensely in eliminating crime in Northern Nigeria, to be specific a purposeful sampling method is adopted in the selection of three states from the three geo-political zones in Northern Nigeria. They are: Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Benue,

Kogi, Nasarawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba.

Keywords: *Maqāsid Ash-Sharī'ah, Kidnapping, Crime, Northern Nigeria, Unemployment.*

INTRODUCTION

Kidnapping was not known to Northern Nigeria in the last two decades, but from 2015 it has become a theme of discussion in the nation's media houses, both printed and electronics. It seems as an avenue for making quick money where the perpetrators demands funds for ransom from the family of a victim through the phone conversation. It is very hard to listen to or read the news without hearing about kidnapping case on daily or weekly basis, there was a time when passengers and travellers had shun the use of Abuja to Kaduna road because of the persistent of the act of kidnapping, then the patronage of rail increases because of the unsafety of the road. Adam Yahya Yusuf shared a view that Islamic scholars perceive kidnapping as an evil consequences and it is as a result of poor governance and law should be fully implemented soul for soul (interview with Yusuf 19/08/202) the This research intend to look at the higher objectives of Islamic law (*Maqāsid Ash-Sharī'ah*) on crime prevention in the society.

The aim of Islam as a religion is to have a society free of crime, anarchy, disturbance, disorder and threatening of a fellow human being, these aforementioned negative attitudes which are concocted by devil minds and perpetrators of act of lawlessness are not only restricted against human beings but even the animals and other creatures on earth. The perception of Muslims on kidnapping in Northern Nigeria is annoying and on its persistence despite several efforts by the government Dutsen Amare says perhaps some people might have interest in the activities (interview with Dutsen Amare 19/08/2021) Allah doesn't want anybody to be cheated, caused to commotion and be troubled, He says:

..... And Allah wills no injustice to the '*Ālamīn* (mankind, jinn and all that exists) (Q 3:108).

Al-Raysuni quoted Al-Shatibi saying that divinely revealed laws have all been established to preserve human beings' interest both in this life and the life to come (Al-Raysuni 223). Islamic law is mainly to protect the right of human beings without bias or any form of discrimination, so anything contrary to this is un-Islamic Al-Raysuni stated that maqāsid are

the purposes which the laws was established to fulfil for the benefit of mankind (Al-Raysuni xxiii).

Kidnapping has become a global problem which requires more effort and strategies to address it and many people involved either because of unemployment or in order to perpetuate in crime in order to achieve their desires best known to them. The term has been defined by many authors for instance, to Mike, Kidnapping refers to the abduction and captivity of a person, typically to obtain a ransom. Sometimes kidnappers hold their captives longer in order to demand more money from the victim's relatives or associates (Mike n.p). Kidnapping is holding someone with the motive of keeping such a person under hide and captivity without revealing the place of his/her hiding, it is purely done for so many reasons which include political, fund generation and assassination as well.

Kidnapping and abduction are sometimes used interchangeably. At common law, kidnapping consisted of the forcible abduction or stealing or carrying away of a person from one's own country to another. Kidnapping is the taking away of a person by force, threat, or deceits, with intent to cause him or her to be detained against his or her will. Kidnapping may be done for ransom or for political or other purposes (www.kidnapping.uslegal.com).

Northern Nigeria, consist of nineteen states out of the total number of thirty six states in Nigeria. The region is seriously facing a lot of insecurity which includes but not limited to *Boko Haram*, banditry, ethno-communal conflicts, farmers and herders crises and kidnapping which is the most disturbing one. Islam prohibits any form of injustice on fellow human being regardless of race, colour, religion and country. Mustapha Abu Sway says Kidnapping is an assault on another, whether a Muslim or non-Muslim. It is an unjust act that God forbids and prohibits: God stressed that the mere differences in religion, even if in the context of a conflict, do not justify assaulting another (<https://www.csmonitor.com>).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Kidnapping has become a worrisome that create confusion in the nation, whereby people are not secured at home and everywhere including offices and market places, government are making a lot of efforts in controlling the situation but it seems as if we are

lacking the security personnel to tackle it and provide the needed security for the citizens. This type of crime is what 'Oudah described as an unlawful act which an offender commits having the knowledge of its illegitimacy ('Oudah go). In previous time, it was the wealthy people and politicians that were the target but nowadays everyone is a target and it becomes a lucrative business for some perpetrators while others partake in order to destabilize the peace of our region.

Research Questions

In order to get detail information on the topic of research considering the areas to cover, it is essential to ask the following questions so as to obtain the necessary data thus:

1. *What is the perception of Muslims on Kidnapping in Northern Nigeria?*
2. *How can the case of Kidnapping be controlled using Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah approach?*
3. *Why is the case of kidnapping persist in the country despite the efforts by the governments?*
4. *How does the issue of kidnapping make people fear and have the feeling of unsecured?*
5. *What are the strategies to apply in creating awareness and sensitization for the citizens to stay away from crime?*

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, this research is aimed at sensitizing the perpetrators of Kidnapping in Northern Nigeria to shun the act and embrace self -esteemed character of making our region and country a better and secured area for businesses to flourish, economic to grow and peace to reign. However, the specific objectives is to:

1. Investigate the sensitivity of Muslims on kidnapping saga in Northern Nigeria;
2. Identify the approach of *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah* in controlling kidnaping;
3. Know the reason that makes kidnapping a continuing problem in the country;
4. Find out the reactions of the citizens and their feelings on kidnapping;
5. Proffer solutions for overcoming the crime.

Significance of the Study

This research is important as it would be useful and beneficial to both Muslims and non-Muslims in understanding that Islam in totality is against any act of terrorism. Policy makers, religious leaders, politicians, scholars, Emirs and chiefs, students and researchers, all can benefit from this

research. It would be a reference material and would contribute to the existence knowledge

Scope of the Study

This work will cover Northern Nigeria alone. Some states were selected from the region to be specific a purposeful sampling method is adopted in the selection of three states from the three geo-political zones in Northern Nigeria. They are: Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Benue, Kogi, Nasarawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba would be used as sample to represent the three geo-political zones in the area.

Research Design

Research design is the structure of the study (Babbie 38). This research involves the use of interview, the survey method would be adopted in this research. A good research is always aimed at ensuring reliability, validity and provides answers to the research questions.

Population of the Study

A population is a group of individuals, objects, or items from which samples are taken for measurement (Mugo 1). In this case thirty (30) people have been interviewed and their responses are documented and analysed, the number serve as a sample for the entire North that is to say each zone is having ten interviewees that cover the states.

Sample of the Study

This is refers to the study of the existing element of a population focused on a fragment of the entire population from which generalizations were made based on the findings of the study (Babbie 54). It is described as the smaller group of element drawn through a definite procedure from a specified population.

As a result of the practical impossibility to comprehensively study the population and since it is not possible for the researchers to reach all the members of the population, the research is limited to a sample size of some people, who were interviewed. A Sample can be defined as a set of respondents (people) selected from a larger population for the purpose of a survey (Mugo 1). Sample also is a proportion or subset of a larger group called a population (Gordon 1).

Methods of Data Collection

This study apply the interview method which include distribution of questionnaire to the people in the study area through the use of research assistants,

the survey method would be applied and surveillance technique will be used for sample size determination. 30 people have been asked to fill the questionnaire across the nine selected states from the nineteen Northern states of Nigeria.

The Concept and Meaning of *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah*

Before discussing on *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah* let us briefly explain what *Sharī'ah* is all about. There is a misconception and misuse of the term *Sharī'ah* one can't say *Sharī'ah* Law, this is wrong it is one thing law is *Sharī'ah* and *Sharī'ah* is Law. Hassan & Elesin in their definition says *Sharī'ah* is an Arabic word which means literally "the straight path" or "balanced path" to be followed (Hassan & Elesin 1). *Sharī'ah* is the path to be followed, it is the path not only leading to Allah, the Most High, but the path believed by all Muslims to be the path shown by Allah, the Creator Himself through His Messenger, Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) (Doi 2).

Allah says about the *Sharī'ah* as His law for humanities to live in a society that would be free of any injustice and discrimination of course He was addressing Prophet Muhammad (S. A. W) and by implication the entire faithful servants:

Then We put thee on the (right) way of religion: so follow thou that (way), and follow not the desires of those who know not (Q 45:18).

Let us now have a discussion on the concept and meaning of *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah*. The term *Maqāsid* is a plural while *maqsid* is the singular it is an Arabic word that refers to a purpose, objective, principle, intent, goal, end, telos (Greek), finalite (French) or Zweck (German) *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah* are the objectives/purposes behind Islamic rulings (Auda 2). There are six important purposes of Islamic Law based on level of necessity, they are as follow:

- 1- Preservation of Faith;
- 2- Preservation of Soul
- 3- Preservation of Wealth
- 4- Preservation of Mind
- 5- Preservation of Offspring and
- 6- Preservation of Honour (Auda 3).

If we reflect well and study the above purposes, one can conclude that kidnapers are into this crime on their own and are not representing Islam and Muslims rather it is a deviation from the path of Allah Who commanded for fair and just treatment for the entire humanities and other creatures. He says:

And also forbid transgression and oppression of one another. In several verses of the Glorious Qur'ān he makes oppression unlawful.

.... And seek not (occasions for) mischief in the land: For Allah loves not those who do mischief (Q 28:77).

The essence of Islamic Law is to protect and preserve human life but not to kill people without justification; many texts of the Qur'ān clearly prohibited the killing of a soul without justification. Protecting the right to life is foundational to the building of civilization, without which it is impossible to sustain a civilized culture and achieve technological advancement (Azam 1). Sometimes kidnappers kills the victims either as a result of non-payment of ransom or perhaps the victim is cannot trek for a long distance as it happens with a lecturer of Faculty of Education in Nasarawa State University, Keffi.

Definition of Kidnapping

Kidnapping is a crime that is commonly known in Nigeria by the elderly people, younger ones and even the children. It has become a menace that is gradually getting ground in the country, many scholars defined it in various ways, some of the definitions include but not limited to forcefully or fraudulent abduction of an individual or group of individuals ranging from economic, political and religious to self-determination (Fage & Alabi 289). It is also an act of seizing and detaining or carrying away a person by unlawful means or by fraud, and often with the demand for ransom (Uzoma & Nwanegbo 132). Kidnapping is not a new phenomenon in the globe it has been in existence for a long time.

Causes of Kidnapping in Northern Nigeria

There are many reasons attributed to the continuing perpetration of the cases of kidnapping in Northern Nigeria. These can be itemized as follow:

- 1- Injustice from the side of the government whereby people are denied their rights. For instance, the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provides that all citizens are entitled to basic education, the failure of the government to supply portable water within the rural and urban areas and unstable electricity despite the huge money that is been set aside for that and renewal of power or energy almost yearly where most of our towns live darkness.

- 2- Unemployment, it is another disturbing issue among the youth within Northern Nigeria. A lot of the youth graduated from tertiary institutions but were neither employed nor empowered to start a small business for survival. Malama Zainab is of the view that unemployment and poverty are some of the causes of kidnapping and those arrested should be punished in public (interview 19/08/2021).
- 3- Non-punishment of the perpetrators is another cause of kidnapping in Northern Nigeria. Musa Yusuf Zakariyya, says the only way the case of kidnapping can be controlled is the execution of the kidnappers (interview 19/08/2021) and this in accordance to the following verse of the Qur'an:

And there is for you in legal retribution (saving of life), O you (people) of understanding, that you may become righteous (Q 2:179).
- 4- Drug Abuse, majority of the youth in Northern Nigeria partake in mis-administration of medicine and drug abuse as a result it leads them to think in a negative way and easily engage in any type of crime that come their way.

Quick Money Syndrome, According to Dodo "one of the causes of kidnapping in Nigeria is the rich quick syndrome" most of the Northern Nigeria residents are not willing to strive at the same time, survival of the fittest is the norm in the region, thus you cannot harvest what you do not sow. Most of the youth have lofty dreams and aspiration and as a result the quick rich syndrome without working hard to achieve those dreams will result in them venturing into kidnapping.

It seems that for any act whether of good or bad there is a reason that makes people to think of it, plan for it, carry and execute it, it may be as a result of the injustice by the government that attributes to the causes of kidnapping in Northern Nigeria, this view is supported with an argument that many youth who had graduated are left without employment and the gap between the rich in the country and the poor is wide. Some interviewees related the causes of kidnapping basically on three things, firstly, disrespect to the law of the land, it is a lucrative business to the perpetrators and also to give a government a bad image.

Few Cases of kidnapping in Northern Nigeria

a- The North Western Nigeria

Starting from the recent one in North West specifically Kano state is the case of Hanifa Abubakar that attracts so many comments and lamentations, in fact the abductor of a school girl happened to be a proprietor of a private school, this is a breach of trust. According to the report by Punch Newspaper through its reporter by name Sodiq Oyeleke on 20th January, 2022 with the title "The Abductors of a five-year-old Kano girl, Hanifa Abubakar, have killed her despite collecting ransom." Abubakar's uncle, Suraj Suleiman, confirmed the killing and recovery of her remains at a private school in Tudunwada area of Kano to Daily Nigerian.

It was learnt that one of the abductors took the victim to his wife, but the wife refused to keep her. The uncle said, "The kidnapper first took Hanifa to his wife, but the wife refused to keep her. He then took her to Tudunwada where he operates a private school and then laced her tea with rat poison." After she was poisoned to death, the kidnappers then cut her body into pieces and buried them within the school. "The police on Thursday confirmed that the remains of the five-year-old girl were discovered in a shallow grave on private school premises in Nassarawa Local Government Area, Kano State. After abducting Hanifa on December 2, 2021, the abductors took her to a hideout and contacted her relatives for N6 million ransom (<https://www.punch.com>).

In Katsina state there is a report on kidnapping by Premium Time through its reporter Mohammed Babangida in August 19th, 2021 with the title "Bandits Abduct 10 Students, Teacher in Katsina" The police say the students, on their way home, met the hoodlums coming into the village, "and the hoodlums took the opportunity to grab the students and they took them away on their motorbikes."

Armed bandits, Tuesday evening, abducted nine students of an Islamiyya school in Sakkai village in Faskari LGA, Katsina State, the police have said. Premium Times spoke to two residents of Faskari, who confirmed the abduction, but said the bandits also kidnapped one of the school's teachers. The police spokesperson in the state, Gambo Isa, said the children were returning from an evening lesson when they were kidnapped. Sakkai is a remote village off the road linking Faskari to Yankara, which makes it vulnerable to bandit attacks.

Faskari is one of the 10 frontline local government areas in the state prone to kidnapping and cattle rustling. "People saw the bandits going to

Sakkai village where they abducted nine male students from the school. The students are aged between 12 and 19. No teacher was kidnapped," Mr Gambo said. "The students were on their way home from school. They were not abducted in the school. The students met the hoodlums coming into the village to perpetrate their crime, and the hoodlums took the opportunity to grab the students and they took them away on their motorbikes."

A local source, Sani Ayuba, said the bandits were seen leaving some villages near Faskari before the students were declared missing. "Today (Wednesday night), my friend from the village who lives in Faskari town told me that the abductors have not made any demand for ransom. But we feel that they would call the family," Mr Ayuba said (<https://premiumtimesng.com>). In Kaduna state also people are experiencing the unrest and ugly activities of kidnapping, the Abuja-Kaduna express way some times is abandoned because of kidnappers and people preferred travelling via rail. According to British Broadcast report titled "Nigeria kidnap: Gunmen seize 140 schoolchildren in Kaduna state" At least eight people were also abducted from the National Tuberculosis and Leprosy Centre in Zaria early on Sunday morning.

Two nurses and a 12-month-old child were among those seized, said a hospital worker. There has been a recent spate of abductions from schools and universities for ransom.

On Monday, reports emerged of another mass kidnapping from a school near Kaduna city, about 80km (50 miles) south-west of Zaria. The mother of a 15-year-old girl who was kidnapped from Bethel Baptist School told the BBC that 140 schoolchildren had been seized by a large group of armed men who arrived on motorbikes and broke down the fence. In a statement, police said gunmen "overpowered the school's security guards and made their way into the students' hostel where they abducted an unspecified number of students into the forest".

b- The North Eastern Nigeria

In North Eastern Nigeria, kidnapping is also a disturbing trend to the security and safety of the people living there and the travellers. The experience in Bauchi state about the kidnapping is also on record Nigerian Tribune Newspaper through a reporter Ishola Michel Buchi on September 8th 2021, reported under the title "Police Arrest Seven Suspected Kidnappers, Other Criminals in Bauchi." Bauchi State Police Command has arrested seven suspected kidnappers including a serial suspect who has been operating

across the state kidnapping innocent people for ransom.

The disclosure was made by the State Police Commissioner, Sylvester Abiodun Alabi while briefing Journalists at the Command headquarters on Friday on the activities of the Command in the last two months. Bauchi State Police Command has arrested seven suspected kidnappers including a serial suspect who has been operating across the state kidnapping innocent people for ransom.

The disclosure was made by the State Police Commissioner, Sylvester Abiodun Alabi while briefing Journalists at the Command headquarters on Friday on the activities of the Command in the last two months (<https://www.tribuneonline.com>). In Gombe state there is a report by Daily Trust Newspaper on 01/03/2022 by a reporter Haruna Gimba Yaya that "Police Arrested Eight for Kidnap, Robbery in Gombe State" (www.dailytrust.com). A bill on kidnapping was enacted to deal with the perpetrators and save the lives of the people. The speaker of Gombe State House of Assembly Right Honourable Abubakar Sadiq Ibrahim stated that: "We the state legislature felt we should do something that will protect the lives of our people" The bill seeks to prohibit any act, move or attempt that has to do with kidnapping.

A report by the Blueprint newspaper with the caption "Kidnappers on the prowl in Taraba state" indicates that as the high rate of kidnapping continues unabated in Taraba state, Andrew Ojih writes on the outcry by residents of the state against this menace that keeps everyone awake all night. No doubt, kidnapping in the country has evolved into a lingering, pervasive security challenges to the extent that it has metamorphosed into a fast-paced and multi-faceted criminal enterprise. Taraba is one of the states that has prevalent record of kidnap cases.

Blueprint investigation reveals that from 2015 to date, over 3, 000 people have been kidnapped in the state. The worst recorded case that has portrayed the state in negative light was the kidnap and murder of the late Hosia Ibi, member representing Takum 1 in the state house of assembly on December 31, 2017. The late law maker was kidnapped by three unidentified gunmen in his home town in Takum on that fateful Saturday night. The chief press secretary to the state governor, Hassan Miginyawa, was kidnapped while on his way from Jalingo to Gembu along Sarti in Gashaka local government area of the state. His abductors demanded for 100 million but the state government, it was alleged, paid over 35 million before he was released. A good number of Taraba people

have expressed their bitterness over the increasing activities of this act in the state. The worrisome dimension now is that the kidnappers have changed their base from hidden places in the bush and relocated to Jalingo, the state capital, where they carry it out unhindered as they go about it freely without any fear while demanding for ransom.

Instances, for instance, unknown gunmen abducted two wives of Alhaji Babaji Dadin kowa, a permanent secretary in the deputy governor's office. The gunmen, according to reports, stormed the residence of the senior public servant located at Yagai area in Jalingo metropolis at midnight by first, firing several shots and as a result, residents of the area fled. It was further gathered that they forced their way into the house but the permanent secretary was not in the house at the time they came. They however abducted his senior and junior wives to an unknown location and began to demand for ransom (www.blueprint.ng).

c- **The North Central Nigeria Police Arrested 2 Suspects Who Buried Wives, Others in Mass Grave in Benue**

The two suspects, both members of a 10-man criminal group, took the policemen around the shallow graves, including dry and abandoned wells, where they buried their dead victims. The suspects: Terseer, alias Bob Tsetse and Orkashima David, alias Cash Money were arrested by the police after leading them to the graves where they buried their victims, including their wives. The suspects, according to ThisDay, were nabbed in Osun State after having fled Benue State following killings, kidnappings and armed robbery activities carried out in Mbamon, Tavachan, Michiche council ward of Katsina-Ala LGA of Benue State in less than three years.

In Nasarawa state cases of kidnapping was recorded for instance, 20 kidnapped victims were said to be occupancy of three vehicles while the former education secretary with the Nasarawa Local government, Mallam Salihu was killed at the scene of the incident while traveling to Toto from Nasarawa Gadabuke emirate council secretary, Abdullahi Baba who confirmed the incident said the gunmen in their numbers came out from the bush and attacked the vehicles plying the road and abducted passengers in three commercial vehicles to the bush Tuesday afternoon. Nasarawa Police Command, Monday said it has arrested 40 armed robbers, prosecuted 30 and convicted 5 between January and December last year. The Command also said it arrested 18 kidnappers and rescued 20 victims within the period of its operations across the state. The state Commissioner of police,

Bola Longe who disclosed this on Monday in an operational statistics, exclusively told vanguard that 70 of the arrested kidnappers have been charged to court while 5 have been convicted. The CP said that 20 suspects were arrested for culpable homicide, while 8 were charged to court and 12 are still under investigation. He added that none of the suspects were convicted within the period, while 40 fire arms were recovered through the efforts of the command.

Kogi state is not left out in the ugly and ungodly cases of kidnapping many cases occurred but here are some few of them: in January 25th 2020 Kogi raid Gunmen strike Kogi state in central Nigeria and [kidnap 14 people](#). Five people are freed and others are held by the armed gunmen. Armed gunmen kidnap 11 people, including eight orphans, in Abuja city. Status: It's not known if the ransom demands were met and the kidnapped freed. January 27, 2020 wedding guests kidnapped. Armed gunmen kidnap 25 people coming back from a wedding in North Eastern Taraba state. The kidnapped are rescued on January 31 after a major police operation.

The kidnappers of the Chairman of Yagba West Local Government Area of Kogi State, Mr Pius Kolawole, have demanded N100 million ransoms before he can regain his freedom.

Our correspondent learnt from a reliable source that the kidnappers put a call through to the secretary of the local government late Sunday as well as one of the family members of the chairman to demand the ransom.

Kidnapping as a Threat to security

Security to one's life is essential to peaceful coexistence and it give peace of mind to the people and government in the country. Without security the citizens loses hope of sleeping with their eyes closed and also it causes unnecessary fear in the hearts of the domestic and foreign investors. Kilani is of the view that:

Islam acknowledges the great danger that can result from crimes of aggression against the sanctity of the Muslim's lives, honour and wealth, and the threat to public security that this can pose in the land. The crimes of kidnapping, robbery, rape and transgression of the Muslim's sanctity by way of open and audacious hostility is considered a type of *muhaarabah* (waging war against Allaah and His Messenger) and doing mischief in the land (Kilani 28-29).

Abduslam Aliyu from Buchi state described unending issue of kidnapping because of insincerity of the people involved in tackling it and he call on

Muslims to desist from the act and says the money collected as ransom is prohibited in Islam (Interview with Abduslam Aliyu 19/08/2021). Kidnappers causes havoc to the victim and torture peoples' life. Suleiman Ibrahim, who was a victim expressed dismay and said he lost one of his teeth in the hands of kidnappers (interview 15/06/2021). Faiza Abubakar and Usman Abubakar says if the government is just and firm all crimes in the country can be reduced (interview 14/06/2021).

Solution to Kidnappings under *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah*

Islam is totally against kidnapping because the act infringes the fundamental rights of human being, it can be compared with brigandage (*Al-Hirābah*) which is highway robbery by its nature, it looks like kidnapping because of some features that involved in the two crimes for instance, the use of coercion to compel a victim to do what the arm robber or kidnapper want is a common feature. Applying the law in punishing the perpetrators of any offence can serve as a lesson to any person that want to partake in such a crime but non-application of punishment can give many people chance of doing it.

Kidnapping is persist because some politicians have hands in it and it is threat to the nation's peace and if the law of retaliation would be applied it can be reduced (interview 19/08/2021). While Zakariyya Hussain Abdulsalam from Kwara state consider kidnapping as bad conduct which is against the teaching of Islam and further says Islamic scholars need to enlighten the Muslims on *maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah* (interview 19/08/2021).

According to Shaikh Muhammad Usman, in order to eradicate kidnapping in Northern Nigeria *zakāt* should be properly given because it will help in bringing an end to the menace of kidnapping and the punishment should be executed in order to send message to the perpetrators (interview 19/08/2021). To Mrs. Fatima Ahmad Babanlungu, in order to get rid of kidnapping there is need for training of strong anti-kidnapping agent, monitoring of police activities, serious punishment of offenders and job creation. Some of the solution and approach of *Maqāsid ash-Sharī'ah* in controlling the menace of kidnapping are as follow:

1- Justice; the emphasis on justice in dealings and interactions in Islam is enormous, people were called upon to deal justly Qasim Imam Mardiyya Muhammed is of the view that reimplementation of *Sharī'ah* can help in reducing and eradicating kidnapping in Nigeria on the persistence of kidnapping

cases despite many efforts by the government, she says there is need for awareness and education so that the perpetrators should know the ill regarding the offence. Allāh says:

O you who have believed, be persistently stand firm for Allāh, witnesses in justice and do not let the hatred of people prevent you from being just. Be just, that is nearer to righteousness and fear Allāh; indeed, Allāh is Acquainted with what you do (Q 5: 8).

Jibril Umar and Bashir Ahmad says injustice is among the causes of any form of crime in the country.

2- Consciousness of Allāh; the fear of Allāh will not allow a fellow human being maltreat and kill his brother unjustifiably. Allāh says:

O mankind, fear you're Lord, who created you from one soul and created from it its mate and dispersed from both of them many men and women. And fear Allāh, through whom you ask one another and the wombs. Indeed Allāh is ever, over you, an observer (Q 4:1).

Adamu Usman and Binta Musa were of the view that through Allāh's consciousness people would naturally avoid the acts of crime which is against Allāh and humanity (interview 14/06/2021).

3- Human soul is sacred; in Islam no soul should be killed until if it is legally permitted by the creator Almighty Allāh says:

Because of that, We decreed upon the children of Israel that whoever kills a soul unless for a soul or for corruption (done) in the land – it is as if he had slain mankind entirely. And whoever saves one – it is as if he had saved mankind entirely (Q 5: 32).

4- Kidnapping is tantamount to brigandage (*Al-Hirābah*) which is against Allāh, government of the land, human beings and the society at large, it is prohibited and condemnable in Islam according to Salamatu Idris Doma, the approach of *maqāsid Ash-Sharī'ah* is protection of life and property of every Muslim but kidnappers are on the contrary side and she recommended the payment of *zakāt* and the disbursement should be to all the beneficiaries. The following verse from the Glorious Qur'ān vividly stated the punishment for those perpetrators:

Indeed, the penalty for those who wage war against Allāh and His Messenger and strive upon earth (to cause) corruption is none but that they be killed or crucified or that their hands and feet be cut off from opposite sides or that they be exiled from the land. That is for them a disgrace in this world; and for them in the Hereafter is a great punishment (Q 5:33).

5- Total obedience to Allāh, His Messenger and their law; A believer have no choice in what Allāh and His Messenger have decided, Allāh says:

It is not for a believer, man or woman, when Allāh and His Messenger (S. A. W) have decreed a matter that they should have any option in their decision. And whoever disobeys Allāh and His Messenger (S. A. W), he has indeed strayed into a plain error (Q33:36).

Abduljalil says kidnapping is among what Allah and His Prophet prohibited and lack of patriotism and non-punishment of the offenders is what is making the offence to persist (interview 19/08/2021). Ibrahim Yusuf also revealed that he was kidnapped in 2016 from his resident and was take to unknown destination but later released after paying the ransom (interview 15/06/2021). Alhaji Ajibode was among the victim of kidnapping under their captivity he was threatened either to talk to his people to release the ransom quickly or he would be killed, but later he was released (interview 15/06/2021). By and large Islam as a religion through its law: *-Sharī'ah* guarantee the life of all human beings and prohibited any type of crime against the Creator, government, individuals and the society in general. Any Muslim found perpetrating any crime such as kidnapping, banditry, etc. is on his own but the world especially non-Muslims and the ignorant of Islam should know it clearly that it is not part of Islam and it cannot be found in any of its scripture.

On the strategies of creating awareness on how people should avoid crime imām Hassan Ishaq Sulaiman and Shaikh Kabir Bashir are of the view that by practicing what people learnt through the seminars organizes by scholars kidnapping can come to an end (interview 13/07/2021). Also Sa'id Saleh explained that there is need for kidnapers to repent and desist from the acts that makes people to sleep with their one eye opened.

CONCLUSION

This research concludes that Islam as a religion want to have a society free of crime, anarchy, disturbance, disorder and threatening of a fellow human being, these aforementioned negative attitudes which are concocted by devil minds and perpetrators of act of lawlessness are not only restricted against human beings but even the animals and other creatures on earth. Allah doesn't want anybody to be cheated, caused to commotion and be troubled. The aim of *Sharī'ah* is mainly to protect the right of human beings without bias or any form of discrimination, so anything contrary to this is un-

Islamic. If Islamic law is strictly followed by all and sundry without selfish interest there would be more peace and tranquillity in our nation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After conducting and compiling this research some recommendations which may help in solving the cases of kidnapping are as follow:

1. Since we all agree that kidnapping is an offence against Almighty Allāh and humanity, there is urgent need for the perpetrators to cease from the act and abide by the injunctions of Islam in respecting the dignity of life;
2. Justice is essential in controlling crime in the society all and sundry need to be just in our daily dealings with one another;
3. *Sharī'ah* is a law that regulates the affairs of human beings in this mundane life and the Hereafter if it is so, we should all embrace it as a source of law for our guidance.
4. Government should try to engage students of tertiary institutions and grandaunts in skill acquisition so that after graduation they can be self-reliant with handy work to be getting daily bread;
5. Youth should desist from any crime either for money making or whatsoever reason but they should use their energy in pursuing lawful ventures which can help them build their life and future;
6. Security is important in ensuring the safety of the country and its citizens as such the government should make sure there is strong security in every angle of the country;
7. Citizens should be vigilant and reject any people with bad attitude of committing crime against the states and its people.

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Table of Interviewees

S/N	NAME	OCCUPATION	ADDRESS	AGE	DATE
1	Muhammad Usman	Civil Servant	Lere, Tafawa Balewa Distric Bauchi State	45	19/08/2021
2	Qasim Imam Mardiyyah Mohammed	Student	Aviation Ministry, Lagos	31	19/08/2021
3	Abdussalam Aliyu	Civil Servant	Kurudu Army Estate, Abuja	27	19/08/2021
4	Musa Yusuf Zakariyya	Civil Servant	Gambe, Gombe State	32	19/08/2021
5	Adamu Usman	Business man	Gembu, Taraba State	50	14/06/2021
6	Binta Musa	House Wife	Donga, Taraba State	45	14/06/2021
7	Faiza Abubakar	Civil Servant	Jalingo, Taraba State	30	14/06/2021
8	Usman Abubakar	Preacher	Wukari, Taraba State	40	14/06/2021
9	Jibril Umar	Civil servant	Toro Town, Bauchi State	38	12/05/2021
10	Bashir Ahmad	Politician	Dukku, Gombe State	35	12/05/2021
11	Abduljalil Rbiu Sani	Civil Servant	Doguwa, Kano State	29	19/08/2021
12	Abubakar Isa Dutsen Amare	Civil Servant	Federal University, Dutsinma, Katsina State	40	19/08/2021
13	Adam Yahya Yusuf	Student	Angwan Sarki, Kaduna	38	19/08/2021
14	Zainab Sulaiman	Civil Servant	Federal University, Kashere	34	19/08/2021
15	Ahmad Aliyu	Scholar	Fage, Kano State		11/09/2021
16	Sadis Muhammad	Scholar	Ahmadu Bello Way, Katsina State		11/09/2021
17	Abubakar Abdussalam	Merchant	Daura, Katsina State		11/09/2021
18	Ishaq Yahya	Merchant	Malumfashi, Katsina State		11/09/2021
19	Abdullah Gwani	Scholar	Tudun Maliki, Kano State	57	11/09/2021
20	Babangida Haruna	Merchant	Rigasa, Kaduna State	48	11/09/2021
21	Fatima Ahmad Babanlungu	House Wife	Police Barrack Road, Lafia, Nasarawa State	31	29/03/2022
22	Salamatu Idris Doma	Civil Servant	Nasarawa State University, Keffi	35	19/08/2021
23	Muhammad Baba Aliyu	Student	Kontgora, Niger State	35	19/08/2021
24	Zakariyyah Hussain Abdulsalam	Civil Servant	Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria	39	19/08/2021
25	Suleiman Ibrahim	Civil Servant	Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa	40	15/06/2021
26	Ibrahim Yusuf	Civil Servant	Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa	48	15/06/2021
27	Alhaji Ajibode	Civil Servant	Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa	50	15/06/2021
28	Hassan Ishaq Sulaiman	Scholar	Oturkpo, Benue State	45	13/07/2021
29	Shaikh Kabir Bashir	Scholar	Wadata, Makurdi Benue State	50	13/07/2021
30	Sa'id Saleh	Scholar	Gboko, Benue State	53	13/07/2021